

Potentiometric studies on the complexes of Cu(II) and Ni(II) with some amino acids and 2-(2'-hydroxyphenyl)benzoxazole

Suman Verma and Gita Seth*

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : gita_seth@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 30 December 2009, revised 27 January 2011, accepted 02 February 2011

Abstract : The stability constants of binary and ternary metal complexes of copper(II) and nickel(II) with some amino acids (L-leucine, L-valine, L-serine and L-isoleucine) as primary ligands and 2-(2'-hydroxyphenyl)benzoxazole (HBO) as secondary ligand have been determined potentiometrically at an ionic strength $1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ KNO}_3$ at $35 \pm 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The stability of the binary and ternary complexes are discussed in terms of the molecular structure of primary and secondary ligand as well as the nature of the metal ion.

Keywords : Stability constant, amino acids, 2-(2'-hydroxyphenyl)benzoxazole.

Introduction

Considerable interest in the study of metal complexes with potential ligands has been increased¹. 2-(2'-Hydroxyphenyl)benzoxazole (HBO) is a potential ligand with analytical and other applications².

In the present communication, we report a systematic study on complex formation equilibria between metal ions and HBO and some amino acids (L-leucine, L-valine, L-serine and L-isoleucine).

Results and discussion

Binary metal complexes :

Representative pH-metric equilibrium titration curve for free and metal complexed ligands are depicted in Fig. 1. The proton dissociation constants have been determined under experimental conditions using the Irving-Rossotti method³. The pK_a values obtained are given in Table 1.

Generally, it is observed that MA complexes begin to form at lower pH (~ 3.0) than ML complexes (≥ 3.5). The complexes are quite stable up to high pH values.

The potentiometric titration curves for amino acids in the presence of metal ions exhibits two inflections corresponding to the simultaneous formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complex species. This is due to coordination of the carboxylic group and the α -nitrogen atom of the amino acid to the metal ion leading to the formation of MA chelates.

The binary complex formation of HBO with the metal ions proceeds via a replacement of a proton from the phenolic group of the ligand. These equilibria can be represented as follows – (charges are omitted for the sake of clarity) :

For primary ligand

Table 1. Acid-dissociation constant, stability constants of binary complexes and ternary complexes at $35 \pm 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and ionic strength ($1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ KNO}_3$)

Ligand	Acid-dissociation constant		Binary stability constants				Ternary stability constants			
			Cu(II)		Ni(II)		Cu ²⁺ -A-HBO		Ni ²⁺ -A-HBO	
	pK_{a_1}	pK_{a_2}	$\log \beta_1$	$\log \beta_2$	$\log \beta_1$	$\log \beta_2$	$\log \beta_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{M}}$	$\Delta \log k$	$\log \beta_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{M}}$	$\Delta \log k$
HBO	8.05	-	5.43	10.73	5.07	9.93	-	-	-	-
Val	2.36	9.60	7.79	13.98	6.11	10.73	12.63	-0.49	10.62	-0.56
Lcu	2.37	9.58	8.13	14.05	5.98	10.34	12.68	-0.88	10.45	-0.60
Ileu	2.38	9.59	8.16	13.91	5.80	10.14	12.62	-0.97	10.34	-0.53
Ser	2.21	9.18	7.77	13.47	5.75	9.97	12.44	-0.76	10.28	-0.54

$$\log K_{MA}^M = \log [MA] - (\log [M] + \log [A])$$

$$\log K_{MA_2}^M = \log [MA_2] - (\log [MA] + \log [A])$$

For secondary ligand :

$$\log K_{ML}^M = \log [ML] - (\log [M] + \log [L])$$

$$\log K_{ML_2}^M = \log [ML_2] - (\log [ML] + \log [L])$$

The overall formation constants $\log \beta$ (Table 1) are calculated by using standard procedures based on the calculation of the average number of ligands bound per metal ion, \bar{n} , and the free ligand exponent, pL , from the titration curve (b), (c), (d) and (e) in Fig. 1 using the Irving-Rossotti method³.

Results indicates that MA complexes are more stable than those of the ML type. This behaviour can be interpreted based on the bidentate nature of amino acids which coordinate through the amino nitrogen and the carboxylic oxygen atoms forming the stable five-membered chelate ring. In contrast, HBO act as monobasic bidentate ligand, coordinated through the *o*-hydroxy oxygen and the N-3 atom of benzoxazole ring leading to the formation of six-membered ring.

Ternary metal complexes :

A set of typical titration curves for the different Ni^{2+} -Leu-HBO ternary systems are shown in Fig. 1. The observed lowering of curve (f) in comparison to curve (c) and (e) (binary MA and ML) indicates the formation of ternary complexes in solution.

The MAL complex is considered to be formed in a stepwise manner assuming that MA species formed at low pH region, followed by the addition of secondary ligand HBO in the higher pH region. This equilibria can be represented as follows :

The experimental $\bar{n}_{mix} - pL_{mix}^L$ curve is used to evaluate

the stability constants of the ternary systems.

$$\bar{n}_{mix} = \frac{(V^{III} - V^{II})(N - E^0)}{(V^0 - V^{II})n_A T_{M^0}}$$

$$pL_{mix}^L = \log_{10} \left[\frac{\sum_{n=0}^{n=i} \beta_n^H (1/\text{antilog } \beta)^n (V^0 - V^{II})}{T_L^0 - nT_{M^0}} \cdot \frac{1}{V^0} \right]$$

$$\log K = pL_{mix}^L - \log (1 - \bar{n}_{mix})/\bar{n}_{mix}$$

The relative stability of a ternary complex MAL as compared to its corresponding binary complex ML can be quantitatively expressed by the following eq. (6).

$$\Delta \log K = \log \beta_{MAL} - (\log K_{MA} + \log K_{ML}) \quad (6)$$

The values of $\Delta \log K$ depends on the geometry of the complex, and should be negative^{4,5}, generally between -0.5 and -2.0. A positive or less negative $\Delta \log K$ value indicates a significant stabilization of the ternary system. $\Delta \log K$ depends on the coordination numbers of metal ion and ligands^{6,7}, the change in $\Delta \log K$ values obtained may also be attributed to the change in geometry of the complex.

For square planar complexes with bidentate ligands, $\Delta \log K$ amounts to -0.6. For a regular octahedral and distorted octahedral geometry, the values are -0.4 and -0.9 units, respectively⁴.

Some general observations about the behaviour of the various systems are discussed in the following :

(a) The overall stability constant values of the same metal ion binary or ternary complexes decreases according to the following order - (charges are omitted) :

This behaviour can be mainly explained in terms of the decrease in basicity of the amino acid in the same direction.

Valine, leucine and isoleucine behaves as bidentate ligand and coordinates through adjacent carboxylic and amino groups, thus forming a five membered chelate ring. The high stability of the valine complexes is due to less steric hindrance caused by the chain length, that is increased in case of leucine and isoleucine complexes.

Serine acts as a tridentate ligand, but the position of

Fig. 1. Titration curves for Ni(II)-Leu-HBO (35 °C, $I = 1.0 M KNO_3$): (A) free acid, (B) Leu, (C) HBO, (D) Ni(II)-Leu, (E) Ni(II)-HBO, (F) Ni(II)-Leu-HBO.

the three donor groups renders them sterically unfavourable for effective tridentate coordination. This is in agreement with the lower stability of its complexes than that of other metal complexes.

(b) In terms of the nature of metal ion, the complex stabilities follow the trend $Cu(II) > Ni(II)$, which is in agreement with the decrease in ionic potential or Irving-Wil-liams order⁸.

(c) The $\Delta \log K$ values for all binary and ternary systems under study, are negative in accordance with statistical, steric and electrostatic factors, resulted in lower stability constants for ternary systems as compared with corresponding binary systems.

Experimental

All the chemicals and reagents used were of analytical reagent grade (Merck). The HBO was prepared and purified by known procedure⁹. Yield (56%), m.p. 124.78 °C (Found: C, 74.08; H, 4.32; N, 6.56. Calcd. for $C_{13}H_9NO_2$ (for molecular mass 211): C, 72.92; H, 4.29; N, 6.63%); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$, 300 MHz): 11.48 (1H, s), 8.04 (1H, dd, J 7.9, 1.7 Hz), 7.71–7.75 (1H, m), 7.59–7.63 (1H, m), 7.36–7.48 (3H, m), 7.13 (1H, dd, J 8.2, 0.9 Hz), 7.02 (1H, t, J 7.6 Hz).

The stock solution of HBO was prepared in ethanol and all other solutions were prepared using doubly distilled water. The solutions of metal ions, HNO_3 and KOH were standardized by known methods¹⁰.

pH-measurements were carried out with Systronics digital pH-meter (accuracy ± 0.01 pH) equipped with a combined glass and calomel electrode at 35 ± 1 °C.

The pH-metric readings in 75% (v/v) water-ethanol were corrected by the method of Van Uitert and Hass¹¹.

The pH-metric titration of 50 ml of acidified solution containing 1 : 1 : 1 (M : A : L) molar solution of ternary systems were carried out against KOH solution in water-ethanol (75% v/v) medium at 35 °C and 1.0 mol/dm³ KNO_3 ionic strength.

Multiple titrations were carried out for each system. The solutions were titrated according to the following scheme :

- HNO_3 (0.04 mol/dm³) + KNO_3 (1.0 mol/dm³)
- Solution 'a' + Leu (0.01 mol/dm³)
- Solution 'b' + $Cu(II)/Ni(II)$ (0.01 mol/dm³)
- Solution 'a' + HBO (0.01 mol/dm³)

(e) Solution 'd' + Cu(II)/Ni(II) (0.01 mol/dm³)

(f) Solution 'e' + Leu (0.01 mol/dm³)

Acknowledgement

We are grateful to the CSIR, New Delhi for financial support, the Head, Chemistry Department, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur for laboratory facilities, CDRI, Lucknow for elemental analysis.

References

1. R. K. Lonibala, T. R. Rao and R. K. B. Devi, *J. Chem. Sci.*, 2006, **118**, 327; T. R. Burman and G. N. Mukherjee, *J. Chem. Sci.*, 2006, **118**, 411; N. Raman, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **84**, 29; S. Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **84**, 93.
2. H. Freiser, *Analyst*, 1952, **77**, 830; C. Cimernan and V. Parlo, *Microchim. Acta*, 1958, 259; Z. Holzbecher, *Collect. Czech. Commun.*, 1978, **43**, 3325.
3. H. M. Irving and H. S. Rossotti, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397; 1954, 2904.
4. H. Sigel, "Metal Ions in Biological Systems", Vol. 2, Dekker, New York, 1973.
5. B. E. Fischer and H. Sigel, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1979, **18**, 425.
6. B. Sen, *Anal. Chem. Acta*, 1962, 515.
7. V. S. Sharma and T. J. Schubert, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1969, **46**, 506.
8. H. Irving and R. J. P. Williams, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3192.
9. D. W. Hein, R. J. Alheim and J. J. Leavitt, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 427.
10. A. I. Vogel, "Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis". 4th ed., ELBS, London, 1985.
11. L. G. Van Uitert and C. G. Hass, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **75**, 451.